

Using Folktales to Motivate Students In Learning English.

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Abstract

Creating an English-learning environment during which learners are highly motivated is usually challenging for EFL teachers. This essay suggests how folktales are often integrated for improving reading skills, with a view to enhancing quick learning, encouraging class participation and widening of students' vocabulary. Using folktales in an ESL/EFL classroom isn't a replacement concept. Many teachers have found these ancient stories to be useful for learning during this paper I will be able to explore some rationale for utilizing a student's culture, folktales especially so as to extend reading skills. The essay concludes that a careful use of folktales by teachers helps in motivating individuals and shaping their attitudes to life. It also submits that students don't only understand language faster by learning via folktales, but their vocabulary is additionally widened, their reading skill is additionally improved, and at an equivalent time, culture is additionally acquired.

Keywords: folk stories; reading skills

1. Introduction

Teaching and learning process within the schools can't be separated from curriculum. Curriculum may be a plan designed to expedite the training process under the guidance and responsibility of the varsity or institution and its faculty (Nasution, 2008: 5). Curriculum is consistently evolving in line with the event of the idea and practice of education. Muhammad Nuh because the ministry of education and culture stated that a replacement curriculum are going to be imposed within the school year 2013-2014 (www.seputar-indonesia.com). Teaching model at the faculties are going to be more directed to the character building and therefore the character building are going to be integrated to all or any subjects within the school, including English. Furthermore, within the teaching and learning English process, students' motivation is extremely important, a bit like Corder's phrase in Skehan (1989: 49), 'Given motivation, anyone can learn a language'. Although the curriculum is sweet, but

if the scholars don't have motivation in learning, the teaching and learning process won't running well. The writer within the experience as an English teacher found that there have been many students still very passive during the teaching and learning process. The passiveness of the scholars may caused by their lack of motivation in learning. As Wlodkowski (2004: 12) said, "Behavior caused by things greatly suffering from what proportion motivation inflicted on the scholars themselves". Therefore, the teacher should be smart to settle on an approach that's suitable with the curriculum, and also ready to motivate the scholars to find out.

2. Method

1. Reasons for Using Literary Texts in Foreign Language Classes.

According to Collie and Slater (1990:3), there are four main reasons why language teachers use literature, including folktales, within the classroom.

- 1.1. Valuable Authentic Material Most of literary works aren't created for the first purpose of teaching a language, but the very fact we will use it in our teaching and learning of English within the classroom. That's why we will simply say that literature is authentic material. we will see authentic samples of language in real-life contexts for instance travel timetables, city plans, forms, pamphlets, cartoons, advertisements, newspaper or magazine articles which are included within recently developed course materials. Then, literature can act as a beneficial complement to such materials. By reading literary texts students can with language intended for native speakers and thus they gain additional familiarity with many various linguistic uses, forms, and convention of the transcription.
- 1.2. Cultural Enrichment Reading the literature is a method to urge understanding of the way of lifetime of the country where the target language is spoken. A reader can discover their thoughts, feeling, customs, possession, believe, fear, how they speak and behave behind. Literature is best seen as a complement to other

material went to increase the foreign learner's insight into the country whose language been learnt.

2. *Using Folktales in Teaching English* Although they're certainly valuable in their title –as good stories, as literature, as social and cultural expression, and as moral teaching – folktales have many special characteristics that make them exceptionally good for teaching. Their frequent repetitions make them excellent for reinforcing new vocabulary and grammar. Many have natural rhythmic qualities that are useful for performing on stress, rhythm, and intonation in pronunciation. and therefore the cultural elements of folktales help both bridge footing between cultures and convey out cultural differences – developing cultural awareness that's essential if we are to find out to think in another language and understand the people that speak it. Folktales slot in not only literature but also with sociology, history, religion, and anthropology. due to their natural moral nature, folktales slot in values education. they're excellent for addressing listening, speaking, reading, and writing – either separately or in integration with one another due to many various version and sorts of potential activities, they're especially suitable to be used within the multilevel classroom. due to their flexibility, folktales also can be easily integrated with a spread approaches to teaching.

3. *Using Folktales to Motivate Students in Learning English.*

In the case of scholars have low motivation in learning English and therefore the teacher should be smart to settle on the approach that suitable with the curriculum, the author thinks that teaching and learning activity supported the language experience approach (LEA) using folktale is that the right choice. Taylor (2006: 79) said that: “Students learn most effectively once they are working with materials they're attached to curious about , and that they are most attached to and curious about materials that are about their own lives or they need composed themselves – that's , some sort of self-expression. Folktales are often a crucial a part of people's heritage and cultural identity.”

3. Results

Although they are certainly valuable in their own right –as good stories, as literature, as social and cultural expression, and as moral teaching – folktales have many special characteristics that make them exceptionally good for language teaching. Their frequent repetitions make them excellent for reinforcing new vocabulary and grammar. Many have natural rhythmic qualities that are useful for working on stress, rhythm, and intonation in pronunciation. And the cultural elements of folktales help both bridge common ground between cultures and bring out cultural differences – developing cultural awareness that is essential if we are to learn to think in another language and understand the people who speak it.

Folktales fit in not only literature but also with sociology, history, religion, and anthropology. Because of their natural moral nature, folktales fit in values education. They are excellent for addressing listening, speaking, reading, and writing – either separately or in integration with each other. Because of many different version and varieties of potential activities, they are especially suitable for use in the multilevel classroom. Because of their flexibility, folktales can also be easily integrated with a variety approaches to language teaching.

4. Discussion

In the case of students have low motivation in learning English and the teacher should be smart to choose the approach that suitable with the curriculum, the writer thinks that teaching and learning activity based on the language experience approach (LEA) using folktale is the right choice. Taylor (2006: 79) said that:

“Students learn most effectively when they are working with materials they are attached to interested in, and they are most attached to and interested in materials that are about their own lives or they have composed themselves – that is, some form of self-expression. Folktales are often an important part of people’s heritage and cultural identity.”

There are many ways to perform folktales in the classroom. In this paper, the writer shows one of them, that is eliciting stories from students. This activity requires a fair amount of individual attention for each student.

- 1) Ask the students to tell you a short story from his or her culture.
- 2) The students write it down, correcting the grammatical mistakes. An aide or a more advanced student can also help with this step.
- 3) Give the story back to the student and have him or her read it. This helps the student with reading since the material is very familiar to the student.
- 4) Have the student revise and expand the story to work on writing.
- 5) The student has to be the word master of his or her story.
- 6) Ask the some students tell the story in front of the class, while the others are listening.
- 7) Let the students give mutual correction with the wrong pronunciation. If nobody aware with the wrong one, the students may correct it.
- 8) Discussing the moral value of the stories and ask the students to practice the good ones and avoid to do the bad ones in their live.
- 9) If possible, publish selected stories by each student.

By doing the procedure, the students will learn many things in one activity, they are; the skill of speaking, listening, writing, and reading; they also learn about grammar, verb, and pronunciation in the same time. The teacher may do the procedure completely or just some parts of them. This activity is available with all class level of the students and it can be done in pairs or individuals. The approximate class time is varies, based on the need of the class.

To know whether the students are motivated by the activity or not is by seeing the motivation characteristics showed by the students. Sadirman (2012: 83) explained the characteristics of a person motivated, they are:

- 1) Diligent in facing the task (he can work continuously for a long time and does not stop before the finish).

- 2) Not quickly despair. He does not require a push from outside to participate as possible (not easily satisfied with the achievements of the accomplishments that he has been achieved).
- 3) Showing interest in various problems.
- 4) Preferring to study independently.
- 5) Quickly bored with routine tasks (things that are mechanical, repetitive, and not creative).
- 6) He can maintain his opinion.
- 7) Not easily loose the things that he has been believed.
- 8) Often finding and solving problems.

Those characteristics can be the measurable aspects in assessing the students' motivation. It is classified into several dimensions that can be used as indicator (Miftahuddin, 2012). They are:

- 1) Persistence in learning (sub-variable)
 - a) Attendance at school (indicator)
 - b) Following the teaching and learning process in the classroom (indicator)
 - c) Studying at home (indicator)
- 2) Diligent in facing the task (sub-variable)
 - a) Attitude toward the task (indicator)
 - b) Efforts to overcome the task (indicator)
- 3) Showing interest in various problem (sub-variable)
 - a) The habit learning (indicator)
 - b) The spirit in following teaching and learning process (indicator)
- 4) Achievement in learning (sub-variable)
 - a) The desire for achievement (indicators)
 - b) Qualifying results (indicators)
- 5) Preferring to study independently (sub-variable)
 - a) Completion of tasks/homework (indicator)
 - b) Using opportunities to study outside the school hours (indicator)

If students have the indicators above, it means that they have a strong motivation in the learning process. These things should all be understood by the teachers, in order to interact with the students to provide the proper and optimal motivation.

5. Conclusions

Using folktales in the language teaching will make the students more motivated in the teaching and learning process because they know and like the materials, and they can also learn to act like their heritage teach them to be a good person and it will fulfill the character based curriculum. Therefore, the writer assumes that using folktales in the teaching and learning process which is integrated to the new curriculum will gain the students' motivation in learning English.

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